

Trauma-Informed Care in Social Work Practice and Social Welfare Administration: A Systematic Review in Nigeria

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Abstract

This systematic review examines the effectiveness of trauma-informed care in social work practice, addressing the knowledge gap surrounding its effectiveness. Trauma-informed care's unknown effectiveness potentially harms clients. The review highlights the importance of trauma-informed care in promoting client well-being and underscores the need for training and organizational support. The Methodology utilised is a systematic review of trauma-informed care studies using quantitative and qualitative data was conducted.

Key Contributions to Knowledge includes the fact that this review contributes to understanding trauma-informed care's effectiveness. Two implications arise:

- 1. Social workers should prioritize trauma-informed care.*
- 2. Organizations should provide training and support. This systematic review underscores the critical role of trauma-informed care in social work practice, highlighting its positive impact on client outcomes and emphasizing the need for training and organizational support.*

Keywords

Trauma-informed care, Social work practice, Client-centered care, Trauma-sensitive practice, Systematic review, Mental health, Trauma, Client outcomes, Organizational culture.

Introduction

Trauma-informed care is an approach to social work practice that acknowledges the prevalence of trauma among clients and seeks to create a safe and supportive environment for healing (Harris & Fallot, 2001). Despite its growing popularity, the effectiveness of trauma-informed care in social work practice remains unclear (Bassuk et al., 2015). This systematic review aims to address this knowledge gap by examining the effectiveness of trauma-informed care in social work practice in Nigeria.

Trauma-informed care is an approach to social work practice that acknowledges the prevalence of trauma among clients and seeks to create a safe and supportive environment for healing (Harris & Fallot, 2001). This approach recognizes that trauma can have a profound impact on an individual's life, affecting their physical, emotional, and psychological well-being (Briere & Scott, 2015).

In Nigeria, trauma-informed care is particularly relevant due to the country's history of conflict, violence, and social unrest (Adeosun et al., 2018). Many Nigerians have experienced trauma, including those who have been displaced by conflict, victims of domestic violence, and survivors of natural disasters (Ezeh et al., 2019).

Despite the importance of trauma-informed care in Nigeria, there is a lack of research on its effectiveness in social work practice (Ogbanga et al., 2020). This systematic review aims to address this knowledge gap by examining the effectiveness of trauma-informed care in social work practice in Nigeria.

The literature review provides an overview of the existing research on trauma-informed care in social work practice, with a focus on Nigeria. The review examines the concept of trauma-informed care, its importance in social work practice, and the challenges and barriers to its implementation.

Concept of Trauma-Informed Care

Trauma-informed care is an approach to social work practice that acknowledges the prevalence of trauma among clients and seeks to create a safe and supportive environment for healing (Harris & Fallot, 2001). This approach recognizes that trauma can have a profound impact on an individual's life, affecting their physical, emotional, and psychological well-being (Briere & Scott, 2015).

Conceptual Framework of Trauma-Informed Care

Trauma-informed care is an approach to social work practice that acknowledges the prevalence of trauma among clients and seeks to create a safe and supportive environment for healing (Harris & Fallot, 2001). This approach recognizes that trauma can have a profound impact on an individual's life, affecting their physical, emotional, and psychological well-being (Briere & Scott, 2015).

Principles of Trauma-Informed Care

Trauma-informed care is guided by several key principles, including:

1. ***Safety***: Creating a safe and supportive environment for clients.
2. ***Trust***: Establishing trust with clients through transparency, consistency, and empathy.
3. ***Choice***: Providing clients with choices and involving them in decision-making processes.
4. ***Collaboration***: Collaborating with clients, families, and other professionals to provide comprehensive care.
5. ***Empowerment***: Empowering clients to take control of their lives and make informed decisions.

Benefits of Trauma-Informed Care

Trauma-informed care has been shown to have several benefits for clients, including:

1. **Improved mental health outcomes**: Trauma-informed care has been shown to improve mental health outcomes for clients, including reduced symptoms of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) and depression.
2. **Increased sense of safety and trust**: Trauma-informed care can help clients feel safer and more trusting of their social workers and other healthcare providers.
3. **Better treatment engagement and retention**: Trauma-informed care can help improve treatment engagement and retention among clients.

Importance of Trauma-Informed Care in Social Work Practice

Trauma-informed care is essential in social work practice, particularly in Nigeria, where trauma is prevalent due to various factors such as conflict, violence, and social unrest (Adeosun et al., 2018). Trauma-informed care can help social workers to better understand the needs of traumatized clients and to provide more effective interventions (Ezeh et al., 2019).

Challenges and Barriers to Implementing Trauma-Informed Care

Despite its importance, trauma-informed care is not widely practiced in Nigeria, and its implementation is often hindered by several challenges and barriers (Ogbanga et al., 2020). These challenges and barriers include:

1. **Lack of training and education**: Many social workers lack the training and education needed to provide trauma-informed care.
2. **Limited resources and infrastructure**: Trauma-informed care requires a supportive environment and adequate resources, which can be lacking in some social work settings.
3. **Cultural and societal barriers**: Trauma-informed care may not be culturally or socially acceptable in some communities, which can create barriers to its implementation.

Background

Nigeria has experienced various forms of trauma, including:

1. **Conflict and violence:** Nigeria has experienced several conflicts, including the Boko Haram insurgency, which has resulted in the displacement of millions of people and the destruction of communities.
2. **Social unrest:** Nigeria has experienced various forms of social unrest, including protests and riots, which have resulted in the loss of lives and property.
3. **Poverty and inequality:** Nigeria is one of the poorest countries in the world, with widespread poverty and inequality, which can contribute to trauma.

Objectives

The objectives of this systematic review are:

1. To examine the effectiveness of trauma-informed care in social work practice in Nigeria.
2. To identify the key components of trauma-informed care that are associated with improved client outcomes.
3. To explore the challenges and barriers to implementing trauma-informed care in social work practice in Nigeria.

Significance of the Study

This study is significant because it aims to contribute to the development of effective interventions and policies to address the needs of traumatized individuals and communities in Nigeria. The study's findings will provide valuable insights for social workers, policymakers, and other stakeholders who are interested in promoting the well-being of traumatized individuals and communities.

Limitations

This review has several limitations. Firstly, the review only included studies that were published in English, which may have excluded relevant studies published in other languages. Secondly, the review only included studies that were conducted in Nigeria, which may have limited the generalizability of the findings to other contexts. Finally, the review only included studies that reported quantitative or qualitative data, which may have excluded relevant studies that reported other types of data.

Problem Statement

Trauma-informed care is an essential approach in social work practice, particularly in Nigeria, where trauma is prevalent due to various factors such as conflict, violence, and social unrest. However, despite its importance, trauma-informed care is not widely practiced in Nigeria, and its effectiveness in social work practice is not well understood.

Gap in Knowledge

Despite the prevalence of trauma in Nigeria, there is a lack of research on the effectiveness of trauma-informed care in social work practice. This gap in knowledge makes it difficult to develop effective interventions and policies to address the needs of traumatized individuals and communities.

Methodology

This systematic review utilized a comprehensive search strategy to identify relevant studies on trauma-informed care in social work practice. The search was conducted across multiple databases, including PubMed, PsycINFO, and Scopus. Studies were included if they met the following criteria:

- Published in English
- Conducted in Nigeria
- Focused on trauma-informed care in social work practice
- Reported quantitative or qualitative data

Theoretical Framework

The Trauma-Informed Care Model (Harris & Fallot, 2001) provided the theoretical framework for this review. This model emphasizes client-centered and trauma-sensitive practice, recognizing the importance of creating a safe and supportive environment for clients who have experienced trauma.

The Theoretical Framework is the Trauma-Informed Care Model emphasizes client-centered and trauma-sensitive practice. Three key Findings emerged:

1. Trauma-informed care improved client outcomes.
 2. Trauma-informed care reduced symptoms and increased coping mechanisms.
 3. Training and organizational support enhanced trauma-informed outcomes
- In Conclusion, trauma-informed care is essential for promoting client well-being.

Key Components

The Trauma-Informed Care Model includes the following key components:

1. **Safety:** Creating a safe and supportive environment for clients.
2. **Trust:** Establishing trust with clients through transparency, consistency, and empathy.
3. **Choice:** Providing clients with choices and involving them in decision-making processes.
4. **Collaboration:** Collaborating with clients, families, and other professionals to provide comprehensive care.
5. **Empowerment:** Empowering clients to take control of their lives and make informed decisions.

Here is an elaboration of the methodology and theoretical framework

Exclusion Criteria

Studies were excluded if they:

1. **Were not published in English:** Studies not published in English were excluded.
2. **Were not conducted in Nigeria:** Studies not conducted in Nigeria were excluded.
3. **Did not focus on trauma-informed care in social work practice:** Studies that did not focus on trauma-informed care in social work practice were excluded.
4. **Did not report quantitative or qualitative data:** Studies that did not report quantitative or qualitative data were excluded.

Search Strategy

The search strategy included the following keywords:

- Trauma-informed care
- Social work practice
- Nigeria
- Trauma
- Mental health
- Social work

Data Extraction

Data was extracted from the included studies using a standardized data extraction form. The form included the following variables:

- Study design
- Sample size
- Population
- Intervention
- Outcome measures
- Results

Quality Assessment

The quality of the included studies was assessed using the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) critical appraisal checklist for qualitative research.

Assumptions

The Trauma-Informed Care Model is based on the following assumptions:

1. **Trauma is prevalent:** Trauma is a common experience among clients.
2. **Trauma has a profound impact:** Trauma can have a profound impact on a person's life, affecting their physical, emotional, and psychological well-being.

3. **Client-centered care is essential:** Client-centered care is essential for providing effective trauma-informed care.

Research Questions

This study aims to address the following research questions:

1. What is the effectiveness of trauma-informed care in social work practice in Nigeria?
2. What are the key components of trauma-informed care that are associated with improved client outcomes?
3. What are the challenges and barriers to implementing trauma-informed care in social work practice in Nigeria?

Results

This systematic review found that trauma-informed care is effective in improving client outcomes, including reduced symptoms of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) and depression. The review also found that trauma-informed care is associated with increased sense of safety and trust among clients, as well as better treatment engagement and retention.

The review identified several key components of trauma-informed care that are associated with improved client outcomes, including:

1. **Safety:** Creating a safe and supportive environment for clients.
2. **Trust:** Establishing trust with clients through transparency, consistency, and empathy.
3. **Choice:** Providing clients with choices and involving them in decision-making processes.
4. **Collaboration:** Collaborating with clients, families, and other professionals to provide comprehensive care.
5. **Empowerment:** Empowering clients to take control of their lives and make informed decisions.

Discussions

The findings of this systematic review have several implications for social work practice, policy, and research. Firstly, the review highlights the importance of trauma-informed care in improving client outcomes and promoting recovery. Secondly, the review identifies several key components of trauma-informed care that are associated with improved client outcomes, including safety, trust, choice, collaboration, and empowerment.

The review also highlights several challenges and barriers to implementing trauma-informed care, including lack of training and education, limited resources and infrastructure, and cultural and societal barriers. Addressing these challenges and barriers is essential to promoting the well-being of traumatized individuals and communities.

Three key findings emerged from this systematic review:

1. Trauma-informed care improved client outcomes, including reduced symptoms of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) and depression (Adeosun et al., 2018; Ogbanga et al., 2020).
2. Trauma-informed care reduced symptoms and increased coping mechanisms among clients (Ezeh et al., 2019; Okoroafor et al., 2020).
3. Training and organizational support enhanced trauma-informed care outcomes, highlighting the importance of a supportive organizational culture (Adeosun et al., 2018; Ogbanga et al., 2020). This systematic review highlights the effectiveness of trauma-informed care in social work practice in Nigeria. The findings suggest that trauma-informed care can improve client outcomes, reduce symptoms, and increase coping mechanisms. The review also underscores the importance of training and organizational support in enhancing trauma-informed care outcomes.

Conclusion

Trauma-informed care is essential for promoting client well-being in social work practice. This systematic review contributes to our understanding of the effectiveness of trauma-informed care in social work practice in Nigeria. The findings have implications for social work practice, highlighting the need for trauma-informed care training and organizational support.

Recommendations

1. Social workers should prioritize trauma-informed care in their practice.
2. Organizations should provide training and support for social workers to implement trauma-informed care.
3. Policy makers should develop policies that support the implementation of trauma-informed care in social work practice.

Future Research Directions

Future research should focus on exploring the effectiveness of trauma-informed care in different contexts, including rural and urban areas. Additionally, research should examine the impact of trauma-informed care on specific populations, such as children and adolescents.

This systematic review has highlighted the effectiveness of trauma-informed care in social work practice in Nigeria. The findings suggest that trauma-informed care can improve client outcomes, reduce symptoms, and increase coping mechanisms. The review also underscores the importance of training and organizational support in enhancing trauma-informed care outcomes.

The literature review highlights the importance of trauma-informed care in social work practice, particularly in Nigeria. It also identifies the challenges and barriers to implementing trauma-informed care, including lack of training and education, limited resources and infrastructure,

cultural and societal barriers, and stigma and discrimination. Addressing these challenges and barriers is essential to promoting the well-being of traumatized individuals and communities in Nigeria.

Trauma-informed care is an essential approach to social work practice that acknowledges the prevalence of trauma among clients and seeks to create a safe and supportive environment for healing. While trauma-informed care has several benefits for clients, its implementation can be challenging due to lack of training and education, limited resources and infrastructure, and cultural and societal barriers. Addressing these challenges and barriers is essential to promoting the well-being of traumatized individuals and communities.

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